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Whitepaper on EnLil

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Tablets, seals and sealings from Near East

This whitepaper related to EnLil (Enhancement of Little curved object representation: cuneiform tablets and cylindrical seals from the Near East) focuses on how 3D scanning methodologies and post-processing analyses can help us gain a deeper understanding of particular archaeological artifacts.

Modern 3D scanners based on the structured-light principle are opening up new possibilities for creating detailed models with micrometric resolutions. This work focuses on 3D scanning and post-processing analysis/filtering artifacts from ancient Western Asia, especially seals and cuneiform clay tablets, fragile artifacts that can contain a lot of semantic information beyond transliteration: e.g., seal impressions (figurative and textual), fingerprint evidence, retracing, and erased text. The ease of use of portable structured-light scanners hides the enormous potential for feature extraction and processing. Metric analysis, such as deviation analysis, coupled with the application of the MSII (Multi-Scale Integral Invariant) filter, enhances data extraction, changing the overall perception of the details of the archaeological artifact. This research approach was illustrated by F. Diara in the manuscript "Data extraction from 3D scanning: post-processing filtering for analytic and informative 3D models of small archaeological finds", published in 2024.

The main dataset related to EnLil is a fundamental part of the archaeological collection preserved in the Royal Museums of Turin in Italy: the archive of cuneiform tablets from the Third Dynasty of Ur (2100 – 2000 BC). These archaeological artifacts, in addition to their textual content, contain further important semantic information that can be extracted through detailed 3D documentation and 3D model filtering. 3D scanning is a fundamental tool for better reading the seal impressions beneath the cuneiform text and understanding the micrometric evidence of the scribes' fingerprints. Most of the seal impressions were made before the writing, like a watermark, and thus are not detectable to the naked eye due to the cuneiform signs above them and their state of preservation. In this context, it has been demonstrated how 3D scanning and post-processing analysis concretely aid the analysis of these almost invisible features impressed on the tablets, also integrating previous studies.

The tablet MAT 68g is an emblematic case. It preserves an administrative document written in the Sumerian language. This tablet, despite its small format (51 mm × 46 mm), was pre-sealed on its entire surface, including the edges. Seal impressions are not always visible to the naked eye and can be seen more clearly in scanned images.

The seal used to make the impressions belonged to the scribe Lu-Haya, who was a member of one of the most distinguished families in the city of Umma. Lu-Haya used several different seals that are documented on multiple tablets from Umma, as reported by Myr 2005 (An updated version of Mayr's PhD dissertation, *The Seal Impressions of the Garšana and the Umma Archives*, will appear in the series CUSAS (vol. 7) in 2024. Publication is in progress).

This tablet was scanned with the Space Spider twice, and a total of 2752 frames were captured. The reconstruction process, via Artec Studio software, returned a 3D model containing approximately 3.6M polygons: fusion processing was set to a 0.08 mm maximum resolution and a 0.16 mm maximum error threshold. Next, the RGB texture layer was computed. By using Artec Studio, the 3D object could be visualized and initially analysed by manually manipulating digital lights. In fact, horizontal and azimuthal light beams can be toggled and manipulated depending on the details to be highlighted. In this way, the individual who analyses the 3D tablet is able to concentrate grazing

lights and shadows to enhance micrometric details. Thus, the early analysis of sealings can be performed by changing light directions. The text and figurative scenes on the underlying seal impressions can be better visualized as well. The potential of this approach is illustrated in the paper by F. Diara "Structured-light scanning and metrological analysis for archaeology: quality assessment of Artec 3D solutions for cuneiform tablets" (2023).

Three-dimensionally documented clay tablets were deeply analysed using post-processing operations based on image computation. In fact, the multi-scale integral invariant filter (MSII) was adopted to extract micro-surface details on polygonal meshes. This filter, implemented inside the open-source software GigaMesh, enhances the micrometric details and features of 3D models, distinguishing different surface depths and layers.

The obtained 3D models were detailed, including the texture layer, and further analyses were performed during filtering operations using GigaMesh. Although the texture conformed to reality, as is detailed later, filtering and shading operations were carried out without the texture layer because these post-processing computations consider only metric and morphologic features and not RGB colours, which may introduce confusion and prevent an accurate analysis.

The cuneiform tablets presented herein were analysed using an MSII filter with changing parameters depending on surface depths: for example, feature vector element (FVE) parameters and colour ramp visualization were managed in different ways for the purpose of boosting the details of each tablet.

Concerning the cuneiform tablet MAT 689, the MSII filter was adopted in two ways: first with 13 feature vector elements (FVEs) and an inverted colour ramp, and then with 5 feature vector elements and a normal colour ramp.

Through this process, the seal impressions in the background could be visualized in different ways by enhancing details on the surface layers. This analysis, via MSII filter, was fundamental for enhancing and revealing unperceived features that lay below the inscribed cuneiform signs. Other filtering processes, such as ambient occlusion and radiance scaling, did not permit such a detailed analysis of the sealings.

Although the sealings on the obverse and reverse were previously visualized and documented by Giovanni Bergamini, our post-processing analysis revealed an additional complete seal impression on the edge of the tablet. Bergamini was probably unable to see and analyse this important detail revealed by the MSII filter, and his drawing of the figurative apparatus of the sealing lacks the details on the edge. The analysis proposed herein constitutes an updated and integrative version of the Bergamini drawing.

Post-processing work allows for a clearer reading of the scene engraved on the Lu-Haya seal that was impressed on the tablet MAT 689. A god sits on a two-niched throne, and the god's raised left arm and an astral symbol, undetectable by the naked eye, are now visible. In addition, the post-processed images clearly show that the figure on the left, who is being introduced to the god, is raising both of his arms.

The work conducted on the cuneiform tablets of the Royal Museums of Turin resulted in the article "Moving Beyond the Content: 3D Scanning and Post-processing Analysis of the Cuneiform Tablets of the Turin Collection", published in a special issue of the journal *Applied Sciences* (2024).

Moreover, as concern tablets analysis, the documentation of fingerprints and the depths of the signs can reveal production processes, scribes' writing strategies, and thus the people behind the artifacts. The three-dimensional models generated within the Artec 3D ecosystem using the Space Spider scanner and Artec Studio software were further analyzed by applying specific filters and shaders. Digital light manipulation can reveal, through the dynamic displacement of light and shadows, particular details that can be analyzed with specific post-processing operations. For example, the MSII filter is a powerful tool used to reveal hidden characteristics such as fingerprints and seal impressions stratigraphically beneath the cuneiform signs. This information can provide new insights into the production and use of cuneiform artifacts, contributing to a deeper understanding of the history and culture of Central Asia. Images of the scribe's fingerprint provides a wider perspective on the life of the tablet and establishes a connection with the humans who made these objects. Scanning the entire corpus of the Turin tablets for fingerprints will aid us in distinguishing between the individual scribes who wrote the tablets, even when their names are not recorded in the texts. On this topic, see the forthcoming article by F. Diara - E. Devecchi - S. de Martino: "Sticky Fingers: 3D Post-Processing Analysis of Fingerprint Impressions on Selected Ur III Tablets".

The integration of semantic information into 3D models offers further advantages. It allows to enrich digital models with contextual data, improving the understanding of the meaning and function of the artifacts. For example, semantic information can include details about the provenance, dating, use, and production techniques of the artifacts, providing a more complete and detailed picture. The creation of an open-access repository facilitates sharing and collaboration among researchers and institutions worldwide. This open approach promotes data transparency and accessibility, allowing a wider audience to access information and contribute to research. The repository can include not only 3D models but also associated data such as photographs, textual descriptions, scientific articles, and other research materials.

1 The limestone relief of Sargon II

Another important aspect of EnLil concerned the metrological and qualitative evaluation of Artec 3D structured-light scanners: these instruments have been tested and evaluated to reconstruct small but also medium-sized archaeological artifacts: Space Spider, and LEO were compared in terms of the complete workflow, from preparatory work to post-processing. In this regard, Leo and Spider scanner were exploited for the 3D documentation and analysis of the limestone relief of Sargon II preserved inside the Archaeological Gallery in Musei Reali of Turin.

The limestone relief fragment (TO 10407, 89 cm in height and 52 in width), which portrays the Neo-Assyrian king Sargon II (721-705 BC), is one of the masterpieces in the archaeological collection of Musei Reali in Torino. This relief comes from the ancient city of Dur-Sharrukin (Khorsabad) in northern Iraq that was founded by Sargon II and was his royal residence.

The site of Khorsabad was investigated by Paul Émile Botta (1802-1870) who, though born in Turin, followed his father in Paris and lived in France. He was appointed as French consul at Mosul and, fond of archaeology, opened excavations before a Nineveh (Tell Kouyunjik) and then a Khorsabad. Botta sent to Paris the slabs which decorated the royal palace of Sargon II, as well as the monumental, winged bull statues that was located at the gates. They are currently exposed in the Louvre Museum. Notwithstanding, Botta decided to donate two pieces, the head of Sargon and another relief

representing a high ranked dignitary, to the Turin Egyptian Museum. These two reliefs reached Turin in 1847.

The practice of removing the stone relief decoration from the walls of the ancient buildings, where they were originally located, and cutting the parts that were considered the most appreciable, was normal in the nineteenth century. Sargon II wears the royal tiara and an elaborated earring in form of a cross. His hair and curled beard are in the royal Neo-Assyrian style. As Carlo Lippolis argued, the kings' face, which appears in profile, mixes a profile view with a frontal perspective. This is evident if we look at the king's eye that is presented frontally.

Besides, the surface of the relief was smoothed on the tiara and the shoulders, likely for removing damages of the stone surface. This operation has cancelled any possible traces of the colours that were applied on the stone.

As mentioned before, Spider and LEO were used for 3D scanning the masterpiece. The Artec Space Spider is a portable optical scanner that employs blue light to capture features, sharp edges, and intricate surfaces on small to medium-sized objects. With a 3D point accuracy of 0.05 mm during the capturing phase and a final 3D model resolution of 0.1 mm, it reveals as a precise and reliable tool for documenting complex and detailed archaeological artefacts. Its sensor operates alongside monitor feedback from the Artec Studio software through a cable connection. This feedback is crucial for reducing drift errors caused by incorrect distances or angles of the operator and for referencing the scanning trajectory.

Despite its high portability and compactness, this scanner encounters some operational challenges, especially related to the acquisition area: in tight and intricate spaces, the scanning process and movement can be risky due to the wired connections and visual feedback on the laptop screen. Capturing archaeological artefacts in confined (horizontal and vertical) spaces may take longer than anticipated and require additional safety precautions. In this regard, the 3D documentation of the limestone relief of Sargon II proved to be complex: due to the fixed position of the relief, a portable stair and cable extension have proven necessary for the survey.

By contrast, the documentation phase occurred with LEO scanner have been performed without issues. This instrument, being totally wireless and having an onboard display and storage, allowed to easily cover the entire surface of the relief. Furthermore, in addition to be extremely portable and flexible, the acquisition speed influenced the 3D survey: in fact, the entire relief was 3D scanned approximately in 15 minutes against the 45 minutes with the Spider sensor. LEO scanner – designed for acquiring medium and large objects - has the 3D point accuracy up to 0.1 mm and the 3D resolution up to 0.2 mm. Despite the acquisition speed is up to 60 frame per second, the scanning session was set to 15 to 20 frames per second for having more control in scan shifting and redundant data.

Raw scan data was processed inside Artec Studio software and, after the scan alignment / orientation and registration, 3D models were obtained by means of fusion operation. The process has returned detailed models having big differences in triangles populations: Space Spider model 140 million of polygons with 0.1 mm resolution; LEO 37 million of polygons with 0.2 mm resolution. These elaborations, extremely useful for understanding micrometric details of the relief, demonstrated that the here used scanners are designed for different purposes depending on objects size. In fact, these outputs were the basis for the next tests and deeper analyses for extracting information from stone surfaces.

Investigation methodologies concentrated on the use of Multi Scale Integral Invariant (MSII) filtering and Virtual Reflectance Transformation Imaging (V-RTI). These methodologies, applied to the 3D model obtained from Space Spider, were exploited for mapping, distinguishing and boosting visibility of damages (intentional and accidental) and abrasions, as well as reading and understanding lost decorations. Due to micrometric evidence and nearly invisible details, these investigations were conducted to the more sharpen and populated model (0.1 resolution).

Furthermore, deviation analysis was carried out for understanding depth values of the relief from the background surface (fitting plane with the background). This analysis, not operating in micrometric evidence, was carried out by using the LEO model (0.2 mm resolution): the most prominent point of the bas-relief is related to the shoulder of the king, that is about 45-47 mm; by contrast the headgear is about 38-40 mm prominent and the face 35-37 mm.

Damage mapping

In this regard, MSII filter was useful for establishing a damages map on the entire surface of the relief: these material leaks could be referred to involuntary as voluntary actions, as for the detachment from the original limestone relief and accidental transportation-related damages.

Abrasions

Then, specific filters and colour scales related to MSII were fundamental to understanding and highlighting linear smoothing (headgear and right shoulder) and chaotic abrasions especially on the left shoulder. In this case, the abrasions follow almost the entire surface of the shoulder and appear to have been made to erase something along the outer area (decorations or visible damages). Furthermore, vertical and horizontal abrasions have been performed on the headgear surface for smoothing or hiding imperfections or other features.

A particular abrasion action occurred on the right arm/shoulder of the Assyrian king. In this case, the abrasions, traced vertically, are clearly visible and stratigraphically partially cover the floral motif. The decorations immediately below are not covered by vertical abrasions and they are different (qualitatively) from the top ones, suggesting that they are retraced 19th century decorations. In this regard, the lost decorations are the focus of the next analysis.

Lost decorations and typological comparisons

In addition to MSII analysis, also the V-RTI investigation had a positive impact for enhancing barely visible evidence concerning lost decoration. This methodology was applied to read and understand smoothed and deleted the original decorative apparatus on headgear and the robe of Sargon II. In fact, as we will see, the standardised and widespread iconography of the Assyrian king is characterized by different geometric, floral and figurative apparatus.

V-RTI analyses on high quality 3D models, conducted via Relight software, have been principally divided in two blocks: the upper area with headgear, the bottom area with the robe and shoulders. Ad hoc grazing spotlights highlighted three circular flowers and a border line at the top of the headgear and, beneath the upper band with circular flowers, the analysis brought out a barely visible middle band as well as a lower one. The middle band shows a nearly invisible lost figurative or geometric apparatus inside. Same analyses with V-RTI were conducted for understanding the position of abrasions on the right shoulder of the king: as mentioned before, the last three floral decoration at the bottom are stylistically different from the top ones, suggesting that they are retraced at a later stage (probably referred to 19th century decorations after detached operations).

After these analyses, we proceeded to map lost decorations extracted from V-RTI and MSII computation. In this regard, the headwear resulted having three levels of decorations: the most visible is related to the top one, which includes floral motives inscribed into circles; then, the middle band is barely visible but with post-processing analyses lost decorations can be perceived and they referred to circular and linear motives probably coupled with figurative apparatus; finally, the bottom decorative band of the headwear resulted totally smoothed and abraded even if the upper boundaries are visible.

Another part of the relief that has been completely smoothed and abraded is the left shoulder. Here the entire surface has been damaged and it cannot be determined whether it had any kind of decoration. The left shoulder also partially shows the robe and the floral motive that appears on the other side.

These analyses and hypotheses were supported by typological comparisons with other portraits of the Assyrian king. In fact, through analyses on detailed 3D models, the extracted decorations were compared with other figurative features found in other reliefs. Important reliefs from the Dur-Šarrukin fortress (Khorsabad - Iraq) were taken into account, in particular the detailed 19th-century drawings by Paul Émile Botta, Eugene Flandin, Hartmut Smokel. These precise drawings of entire wall reliefs validate certain hypotheses of lost decorative apparatus.

The unique information extracted from the relief has been managed and shared inside an open access repository for 3D visualize the model as well as for query semantic data from the limestone surface. Through this viewer, the model is linked to metadata: in this way, it is simple to analyse the relief content, materials, extracted features, metrics, and descriptions. Then, a full-immersion 3D viewer allows to navigate the digital twin of the relief and carry out straightforward post-processing analysis. Historical and extracted metadata can be investigated and related to 3D models using relational and semantic queries based on certain ontologies and standards in the updated repository. In this regard, creating an intelligent, open-access environment will make it easier to update this project as well as to exchange semantic data.

Furthermore, the 3D documentation and modelling project has led to a parallel sharing project for accessibility, educational and inclusion purposes. This project was carried out through a 3D printing operation of LEO model. In fact, after analyses on limestone relief, we tested FormLAB 3L printer to reproduce the limestone portrait of Sargon II in scale 1:3 having dimension 30 x 18 cm. The printer, set to 0.05 mm resolution (layers distance) performed well and the result is detailed, also showing the original abrasions and lost decorations. The printed model, with grey resin V4, after the needed optimization by using Formlab Wash and Cure, has been completed with acrylic painting on base resin. Figure --- shows the 3D printed model of Sargon II. Finally, this replica was presented at the international conference "*Archeologia in vetrina. Archetipi espositivi e modelli di fruizione dell'antico dal '700 all'Era Digitale*" (Archaeology in the showcase. Display Archetypes and Models for the Use of Antiquity from the 18th Century to the Digital Age) in Musei Reali of Turin and the model was donated to the Museum.

The data resulting from the 3D analysis of the Sargon survey and the technical details of the work carried out are illustrated in a forthcoming article by F. Diara and S. de Martino "The portrait of King Sargon II: 3D scanning, filtering and computational imaging for semantic data extraction".

The evaluation and testing of structured-light scanners allow the development of operational protocols that facilitate the documentation of archaeological collections. This process, from scanning to post-processing, provides a valuable tool for archaeologists and scholars, allowing them to examine every minute detail of the analyzed artifacts.

In conclusion, 3D scanning methodologies and post-processing analyses present enormous potential for archaeological research, allowing the extraction of hidden and semantic information from ancient artifacts, improving our understanding and enhancement of cultural heritage. In addition to improving the documentation and analysis of artifacts, these technologies can be used to create physical 3D-printed replicas that can be studied and shared without the risk of damaging the originals. Digital and printed replicas can also be used for educational purposes, allowing students and enthusiasts to explore and interact with detailed models of historical artifacts.

2 References

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